

THE INFLUENCE OF AFFECTIVE FILTER ON THE LEARNING PROCESS: IMPLICATIONS FOR CLASSROOM INSTRUCTION AND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

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Abstract: This study investigates the role of the affective filter in the process of learning, particularly in second language acquisition (SLA). The affective filter that was explored by Stephen Krashen in 1982 as part of his the input hypothesis, is a mental barrier that influence learners' ability to receive input. Psychological factors like anxiety, motivation, self- confidence and attitude promote the strength of this filter. This thesis examines how affective filter influences learning outcomes and by examining key psychological factors mentioned above, will highlight strategies which can be employed by educators to reduce the affective filter, thus creating more effective and inclusive language learning environment.

Key words: Affective filter, Krashen's hypothesis, emotions, psychological barrier, project- based learning, motivation, anxiety, low self-esteem.

Introduction

The process of learning a language is a complex interaction consisting of cognitive, emotional, and social factors. Stephen Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis proposes critical insights into the emotional aspects that influence language acquisition, emphasizing emotions. Emotions play a significant role in learning process and retain new language input because they contribute to acquisition. Tyng et al. (2017) highlights emotion influences the cognitive processes in humans, including attention, language, perception, learning, memory, and thought. Therefore, learners, who are in bad mood or find themselves under pressure, cannot be opened and concentrate, especially while learning foreign language. Prodanovska-Poposka (2023) defines the emotional state of human behaviour as affective domains which are "a general emotional state that affects the perception and production of foreign language learners and such emotions can create a filter for learning a foreign language called an affective filter" (p. 262). The affective filter was introduced by Krashen in his The Input Hypothesis which is defined as a central part of theory of second language acquisition that consists of five hypothesis. One of the most significant part of acquisition is comprehensible input which will be received by a learner, if acquirer is open. According to Krashen (1985), acquirer needs to be mentally open to receive input.

Sajida (2023) defines the concept of "affective filter" as emotional well- being of learners, presenting a mental barrier that can either complicate or facilitate the acquisition of language depending on how high or low it is. A high affective filter, triggered by stress, low motivation, or fear of making mistakes, hinders language acquisition, while a low filter, fostered by positive emotions and conducive learning environments, enhances it.

Theoretical Background

Stephen Krashen's (1982) Monitor Model of second language acquisition involves five hypotheses: the Acquisition-Learning Hypothesis, the Monitor Hypothesis, the Input Hypothesis, the Natural Order Hypothesis, and the Affective Filter Hypothesis, and he points

out that in SLA key factors of learners' success in language learning is associated to the learners' emotional condition (Lin, 2008, p. 115). The comprehension of second language acquisition is influenced both by cognitive factors and emotional well-being of the learners (Swain, 2013). The Affective Filter Hypothesis asserts that emotional variables such as motivation, self-confidence, and anxiety directly influence how language learners process input (Prodanovska-Poposka, 2023, p. 262). According to Krashen (1985), learners with a low affective filter are more likely to comprehend and internalise new language, as they are more open to receiving and processing comprehensible input.

Key Factors Influencing the Affective Filter

Sanesi (2023) lists some affective variables in his article "High school students' affective filter in second language acquisition: Causes and solutions" that prevent learners to receive input during the class. One of affective variables is *low-esteem* which does not allow a learner to complete tasks, because learners underestimate their abilities and skills that they are good enough to complete the task. Consequently, it leads to mental block and students will be closed to get input. Sajida (2023) suggests a strength-based approach which can be employed to boost self-esteem, focusing on students' existing skills and achievements rather than their weaknesses (p. 26). Additionally, giving personalized and constructive feedback to these learners to improve self-esteem, allowing them to be more active in the classroom interaction.

Motivation is one of the most important emotions and is reflected in the learner's strong desire to explore unfamiliar areas (Li & Zhou, 2023, p. 2). Highly motivated learners can succeed in acquiring new languages (Dörnyei, 2005). From the perspective of affective filter, motivation decrease the level of the filter, making learners be opened and receptive to input. Motivation particularly is divided into two types: extrinsic motivation, which means using the results of language learning as a tool to achieve a goal; and intrinsic motivation, which means that learners can gain satisfaction from the learning process and the results (Deci, 1975, as cited in Brown, 1991).

Intrinsic motivation lowers the level of anxiety and increases self-confidence of learners making them to complete all tasks and engage into classroom discussion. Clearly articulating the learning objectives and explaining how they tie into students' personal or professional goals can enhance motivation (Sajida, 2023). Integrating materials and topics that are relevant to the learners' interests and goals, and incorporating intrinsic and extrinsic rewards can help to increase their motivation.

Anxiety is a critical component of the affective filter. Learners who experience high level of anxiety cannot engage fully in classroom interaction as well as task and activities, and challenge in receiving and processing information. MacIntyre (1998) defines the language anxiety as "the worry and negative emotional reaction aroused when learning or using a second language" (p. 27). Horwitz et al. (1986) highlight that foreign language anxiety is "a distinct complex of self-perceptions, beliefs, feelings, and behaviors related to classroom learning arising from the uniqueness of the language learning process" (p. 128). Research suggests that 'anxiety can be considerably reduced by the teacher's encouragement and positive reinforcement, as well as by developing a culture of peer support and collaborative learning' (Sajida, 2023, p. 26).

Teachers play a significant role in minimizing language anxiety in the classroom. Creating a supportive and non-judgemental atmosphere where learners feel free making mistakes is

crucial to lower the affective filter. Making learners work in group, implementing peer support and positive reinforcement can lower anxiety by shifting the focus from individual performance to collaborative learning.

Conclusion

The Affective Filter Hypothesis emphasizes the vital role of emotions playing in SLA. Understanding the influence of mental factors such as motivation, anxiety and self-esteem on learning process allows teachers and educators to create more effective instructional strategies which support students success. By decreasing the affective filter, teachers foster an environment where learners are more open to acquire and process new language skills, leading to greater long-term success. The practical implications of the Affective Filter Hypothesis highlights the significance of making up emotionally supportive classrooms that stimulate active interaction and participation, lower anxiety, as well as foster learners' confidence.

References:

1. Brown D.H. (1991). TESOL at twenty-five: What are the Issues? *TESOL Quarterly*, 25(2).
2. Dörnyei, Z. (2005). *The Psychology of the Language Learner: Individual Differences in Second Language Acquisition*. Routledge.
3. Krashen, S. D. (1982). *Principles and Practice in Second Language Acquisition*. Pergamon Press.
4. Horwitz, E. K., Horwitz, M. B., & Cope, J. A. (1986). Foreign language classroom anxiety. *The Modern Language Journal*, 70(2), 125-132.
5. Li Q. & Zhou Y. (2023). Enhancing EFL Class Design: Affective Filter Hypothesis in Action. *International Journal of Education and Humanities*, 9(3).
6. Lin G. (2008). Pedagogies Krashen's Theory of Affective Filter. *Hwa Kang Journal of English Language & Literature*, 14, 113-131
7. MacIntyre, P. D., Clément, R., Dörnyei, Z., & Noels, K. A. (1998). Strategic competence and the learning of foreign languages. García, E. E., & Orts, L. (Eds.), *International perspectives on teaching and learning research on learning to learn in a second language. The Modern Language Journal*, 82(1), 3-14.
8. On learning to learn in a second language. *The Modern Language Journal*, 82(1), 3-14.
9. Sajida P. & Vijaya K. (2023). The Role of Affective Filters in ESL Classrooms: Fostering Effective
10. Learning Environment. *Humanities and Social Science Studies*, 12(2).